

Utilization of Indian Turpentine. Catalytic Transformation Studies of α -Pinene, Δ^3 -Carene, Camphene and Tricyclene to Cymenes : Kinetic Aspects

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The isomerization and aromatization of α -pinene, 3-carene, camphene and tricyclene to cymenes have been investigated over alumina and chromia-alumina of varying acid strength and also over chromia in the temperature range 235 to 500°. These transformations follow second order kinetics. The isomerization of these compounds depends on the amount and strength of acid sites.

Impregnation of these catalysts with small amounts of potassium ions decreases their isomerization activity and increases their dehydrogenation ability. Hydrofluoric acid does the reverse. Pyridine suppresses both overall conversion and the formation of cymenes.

The ratio p/m^* from 3-carene is higher over chromia than over chromia-alumina. Over chromia-alumina, it increases with the addition of potassium ions and decreases with that of fluoride ions. The p/m begins to fall when the reaction temperature rises above 450°.

TERPENES constitute one of the largest groups of pharmaceutically important natural products. They occur in essential oils derived from coniferae¹. One of the most important and typical essential oil is the oils of turpentine obtained from pine trees. The chief constituents of Indian turpentine are 3-carene and α -pinene which occur to the extent of 50 and 40%, respectively, the rest being β -pinene².

Indian turpentine, though an important industrial raw material, has not been fully exploited in industries. This is because of the unstable nature of 3-carene which undergoes aerial oxidation with resin formation^{3,4}. This renders the oil poor in storage quality.

The major constituents of Indian turpentine, α -pinene and 3-carene, can be aromatized to *p*-cymene and a mixture of *p*- and *m*-cymenes, respectively using chromia and chromia-alumina catalysts. *Para*- and *meta*-cymenes can be oxidised to *tere*- and *iso*-phthalic acids⁵, respectively. Since *iso*-phthalic acid is soluble in hot water, the acid mixture can be separated by hot water treatment. *tere*-Phthalic acid is an important raw material for the manufacture of synthetic polyester fibre while *iso*-phthalic acid is used as an additive in plastics as a heat resistant component. It is to be noted that no substitute for *iso*-phthalic acid for this use has so far been developed. *iso*-Phthalic acid is at present imported to meet the requirements of Indian plastic industries and research institutions. *p*-Cymene can also be hydrated to camphor⁶ and converted to *p*-cresol via its hydroperoxide⁷.

This investigation attempts to obtain kinetic data for the isomerization and aromatization of α -pinene and carene over chromia and chromia-alumina of different acid strengths.

Experimental

Catalysts : Alumina A was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium iso-propoxide according to the methods of Pines *et al*⁸. Alumina B and C were obtained by impregnating alumina A with potassium nitrate solution and hydrofluoric acid (E. Merck ; 40% solution) to give 1.0% by weight of K⁺ as K₂O and 5.0% by weight of HF, respectively. Chromia-alumina A, B and C were prepared by impregnating the corresponding aluminas with chromic acid to give 6% chromium in each by following the methods of Selwood *et al*⁹. In addition, the chromia-alumina A was doped with different amounts of potassium nitrate solutions to give 0.5, 1.5, 2.0, 3.3 and 4.7% by weight of potassium in the catalyst. Chromia gel was prepared by the method of Turkevich *et al*¹⁰.

3-Carene and α -pinene : 3-Carene (b.p. 170°) and α -pinene (b.p. 156°) were obtained from top quality Indian turpentine (supplied by Government Turpentine and Rosin Company Ltd., Bareilly, India) by fractional distillation at 10 mm pressure using a 152 cm glass column packed with stainless steel helices equivalent to 22 theoretical plates. The purity of the materials was checked by gas chromatography. Camphene and tricyclene were gifts from Hercules Powder Company, USA, and used

* $p/m = p\text{-cymene} : m\text{-cymene}$.

without further purification. Details of experimental procedure and analysis of the products are the same as described elsewhere¹¹.

Results and Discussion

The acid strength distribution of alumina catalysts A, B and C and the total acidity of chromia-alumina A and chromia gel were determined by *n*-butylamine titration^{12,13} and the results are given in Table 1. Alumina appears to have a continuous distribution of acid strength although the weak sites

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION OF ACID STRENGTHS OF DIFFERENT ALUMINA CATALYSTS

Catalyst	<i>n</i> -Butylamine titres (meq./g) using indicators				Total acidity
	Anthraquinone ($pK_a = -8.3$)	Chalcone ($pK_a = -5.7$)	Dicinnamal acetone ($pK_a = -3.0$)	Butter yellow ($pK_a = +3.3$)	
Alumina A	0.034	0.056	0.270	0.290	0.650
Alumina B	0.000	0.000	0.230	0.250	0.480
Alumina C	0.200	0.410	0.410	0.420	1.440
Chromia-alumina A	—	—	—	—	0.640
Chromia gel	—	—	—	—	0.140

are more numerous than the strong sites. Impregnation of alumina with HF increases all the types of sites, the increase of strong acid sites being more significant. On the other hand, doping of alumina with potassium ions reduces the amount of weak sites and eliminates the medium and strong sites. The observed variation of acid strength distribution of alumina by fluoride and potassium ions is in good agreement with the observations of Chapman *et al.*¹⁴, Webb¹⁵, Hirschler¹⁶ and Pines *et al.*⁹.

The reaction sequence pertaining to the isomerization of α -pinene to various intermediates and their further dehydrogenation are illustrated in Scheme 1. A similar scheme for 3-carene is given elsewhere¹⁷.

The isomerizations of α -pinene over alumina catalysts A, B and C have been found to follow second order kinetics by plotting $1/(1-x_A)$ against contact time W/F_A (where W is the weight of the catalyst and F_A is the flow rate of α -pinene per gram of the catalyst at 235°). The rate constants calculated from the slopes of the straight line plots are 474.2, 228.5 and 564.9 lit./g mole hr, respectively. The overall conversion of α -pinene increases with increasing acid strength of the catalyst (Table 1), and consequently the value of the rate constant increases.

The isomerization of tricyclene and camphene, the two major cyclic intermediates of α -pinene (Scheme 1), also follows second order kinetics. The value of the rate constant for tricyclene over alumina C at 250° is 289.7, while the value for camphene is only 42.9. The overall conversion of tricyclene is always higher than that of camphene.

The results stated above indicate that under identical conditions tricyclene is more reactive than camphene. This is not surprising because tricyclene contains three bridged rings which impart greater strain to the molecule and consequently are responsible for its enhanced reactivity. On the other hand, the cyclopentane ring in camphene is very stable (the heat of combustion and the angle of distortion are 667 kJ/mole and 0°44', respectively¹⁸) and hence it is not affected especially by weak acid sites.

Another notable feature is that over weakly acidic catalysts, camphene and tricyclene undergo only interconversions and do not undergo skeletal isomerization to monocyclic products. Strong acid sites are necessary for their skeletal isomerization leading to the formation of monocyclic products. This is evident from the fact that no monocyclics are formed over catalyst B under all conditions. Over catalyst A, at a higher contact time of 1.0 hr, tricyclene and camphene yielded 5.6 and 5.4% monocyclic products, respectively which increased to 45 and 40% over catalyst C.

The amounts of *p*-cymene (Fig. 1) obtained from tricyclene and camphene over alumina C are 15 and 13%, respectively which are not much different though there is a large difference in their overall conversions. The higher amount of *p*-cymene (24%) from α -pinene under these conditions is due to the easy cleavage of the cyclobutane ring to monocyclic menthadienes (the heat of combustion and angle of distortion of cyclobutane ring are 688 kJ/mole and 9°44', respectively¹⁸) which are further dehydrogenated to *p*-cymene over the alumina surface.

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on the formation of *p*-cymene from α -pinene, tricyclene and camphene over alumina C.

The dehydrogenation of α -terpinene (over alumina), which is identified to be the immediate precursor of *p*-cymene, may occur by the initial adsorption of a hydride ion by the electron deficient aluminium atom (Lewis acid) leading to the formation of a carbonium ion. The basic oxide ion

subsequently removes a proton from the adsorbed carbonium ion which then gets desorbed as *p*-cymene as outlined below.

Arrhenius plots were made for the isomerization of camphene over alumina A and C in the temperature range 200 to 300°. The activation energies computed from the slopes of these plots are 51.2 and 47.6 kJ/mole, respectively. The activation energy for the isomerization of tricyclene over alumina A is 47.7 kJ/mole. The similar activation energy values involved in the transformations of camphene and tricyclene indicate that the same type of active sites are involved in their isomerizations.

The rate constants for the dehydrogenation of α -pinene over chromia-alumina A, B, C and chromia gel are 1913, 1004, 2097 and 38.5 lit./mole hr, respectively. The corresponding activation energies are 24.9, 19.2, 14.4 and 81.7 kJ/mole. Regarding the formation of *p*-cymene, a higher yield is obtained over less acidic chromia-alumina B while a lower yield is obtained over high acidic chromia-alumina C which decreases further with increasing reaction temperature as can be seen from Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on the formation of *p*-cymene from α -pinene over different chromia-alumina and chromia catalysts.

3-Carene isomerizes over alumina A with second order kinetics involving an activation energy of 48.2 kJ/mole. The rate constant and the activation energy for its dehydrogenation over chromia-alumina A are 2209.9 lit./g mole hr and 44.2 kJ/mole, respectively. When 3-carene is mixed with 2% pyridine, the activation energy increases to 64.7 kJ/mole.

The overall conversion of 3-carene and the formation of cymenes over chromia-alumina A with and without pyridine are given in Table 2. Pyridine suppresses the overall conversion of 3-carene and the formation of cymenes; however, the suppression of the latter is more severe (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF PYRIDINE ON THE OVERALL CONVERSION OF 3-CARENE AND FORMATION OF CYMENES

Temp. °C	3-Carene alone passed			3-Carene mixed with 2% pyridine		
	3-carene reacted	<i>p</i> -Cy	<i>m</i> -Cy	3-carene reacted	<i>p</i> -Cy	<i>m</i> -Cy
360	92.0	40.0	25.0	80.0	24.0	21.0
380	94.0	41.0	27.0	84.0	30.0	21.0
400	95.0	43.0	29.0	87.0	32.0	21.0
425	96.0	45.0	32.0	87.0	34.0	22.0

Pyridine being a weak base ($pK_b = 8.96$) neutralizes only the strong acid sites leaving behind the weak sites unaffected as pointed out by Parry¹⁹. These weak sites are still capable of cleaving the cyclopropane ring which is shown from thermochemical data^{20,21} to be as reactive as an ethylenic double bond. Its heat of combustion and the angle of distortion are 699 kJ/mole and 24°44', respectively which explain its higher activity¹⁹. As a result, the overall conversion of 3-carene is less affected. On the other hand, pyridine molecules may coordinate with the dehydrogenation component, namely, Cr(III) ions and the electron deficient aluminium atom, and thus decrease the dehydrogenation ability of the catalyst (Table 2).

The influence of varying amounts of potassium at 360° on the overall conversion of 3-carene, the formation of cymenes and the activation energies is shown in Table 3. Impregnation of chromia-alumina with small amounts of potassium does not affect significantly the overall conversion of 3-carene. However, the formation of cymenes increases considerably (Table 3). Maximum beneficial effect occurs around 1% potassium. Further additions of potassium beyond 1% decrease both the overall conversion and yield of cymenes.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF POTASSIUM ON THE OVERALL CONVERSION OF 3-CARENE, FORMATION OF CYMENES AND ACTIVATION ENERGY

%K ⁺	Temperature 360°			E _a , kJ/mole
	3-carene reacted	<i>p</i> -cymene	<i>m</i> -cymene	
0.0	92.0	40.0	25.0	44.2
0.5	85.0	36.0	28.0	89.9
1.0	86.0	51.0	18.0	57.5
1.5	72.0	41.0	14.0	55.7
2.0	59.0	29.0	13.0	60.3
3.3	44.0	14.0	8.0	48.8
4.7	40.0	12.0	5.0	36.8

The isomerization of terpene hydrocarbons except 3-carene depends not only on the amount of acid sites but also on acid strength distributions.

The isomerization of α -pinene proceeds via two parallel paths, one giving bi- and tri-cyclic products such as β -pinene, camphene, bornylene and tricyclene and the other giving monocyclic menthadienes such as dipentene and terpinolene over moderately strong and weak acid sites (Scheme 1). Further isomerization, especially of the cyclic intermediates like camphene and tricyclene to monocyclic products, requires strong acid sites. Alumina C is very effective for these reactions followed by alumina A. Alumina B is less-efficient.

Scheme 1

On the other hand, for the aromatization reactions, chromia-alumina B is found to be the most effective catalyst. This can be explained on the basis of the fact that alkali metal ions neutralize the strong surface acidity of alumina preferentially (Table 1).

The strong acid sites of alumina can polymerize the reactive intermediates, namely, the menthadienes, or can isomerize the six membered carbon rings to five membered carbon rings as postulated by Pines *et al*²³. The alkyl cyclopentadienes which would result from such an isomerization reaction can undergo easy polymerization and may deposit on the catalyst surface. The strong tendency of C₅ ring compounds to polymerize when in contact with the acid catalysts and their ability to form complexes with the transition metals and transition metal ions are well known^{23, 24}.

Another factor that affects the yield of cymenes is the occurrence of hydrogen transfer reactions among the menthadienes to form menthenes and menthanes. Higher amounts of menthenes and menthanes are formed over chromia-alumina C followed by chromia-alumina A. Chromia-alumina B is the least active in bringing about this reaction (Table 4a). Strong acid sites appear to influence

hydrogen transfer reactions. Similar results are obtained from α -pinene over alumina catalysts (Table 4b).

TABLE 4b—FORMATION OF MENTHANES AND MENTHENES FROM α -PINENE OVER DIFFERENT ALUMINA CATALYSTS

Contact time (hr)	Menthenes and menthanes (mole %) from α -pinene (Temp. = 235°)		
	Alumina catalysts		
	A	B	C
0.1	0.0	0	5.0
0.2	0.0	0	7.0
0.5	2.0	0	11.0
1.0	4.0	0	15.0

Incorporation of potassium ions neutralizes the strong acid sites thereby suppressing the undesired side reactions mentioned above and thus increasing the yield of total cymenes. For instance, the overall conversion of 3-carene at 360° and at a contact time of 0.5 hr over chromia-alumina B and C are 86% and 94%, respectively and the corresponding yields of cymenes are 69% and 61%. This clearly demonstrates that potassium ions, when introduced in small concentrations, promote the activity of chromia-alumina catalysts. Similar observations have been made by others also^{25, 26}.

Chromia gel is less active both for the isomerization and dehydrogenation reactions (Fig. 2). Isomerization reactions are associated with the acid sites of the catalysts. Compared to alumina and chromia-alumina, chromia gel is less acidic (Table 1). This accounts for its low isomerization activity. From a study of the hydrogen-deuterium equilibration reaction, Selwood²⁷ has shown that chromia dispersed over alumina is more reactive than massive chromia alone which has virtually no activity for H₂-D₂ equilibration reaction. The lower dehydrogenation activity of chromia compared to chromia-alumina is therefore attributed to the poor dispersion of chromium.

The yield of cymenes from 3-carene over chromia gel (17% at 360°) is lower than over chromia-alumina (65, 69 and 61% at 360° for chromia-alumina A, B and C, respectively). The ratio of *p*-cymene to *m*-cymene (*p*/*m*) is 2.4 for chromia gel; it decreases to 1.6 at 450° which further drastically reduces to 0.6 at 500°. Chromia-alumina, when doped with potassium ions (about 1%), increases the *p*/*m* from 1.6 to 2.8 at 360° while impregnation of the same with HF decreases it to 1.0. It is apparent from these results that *m*-cymene is stabler than *p*-cymene over highly acidic catalysts and in the higher temperature regions.

TABLE 4a—FORMATION OF MENTHENES AND MENTHANES OVER DIFFERENT CHROMIA-ALUMINA FROM 3-CARENE

Temp. °C	Menthenes and menthanes (mole %) from 3-carene (t _c = 0.5 hr)		
	Chromia-alumina catalysts		
	A	B	C
360	22.0	6.0	33.0
380	19.0	6.0	32.0
400	17.0	6.0	31.0
425	15.0	5.0	28.0

References

1. J. L. SIMONSEN, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1949, Vol. 2, p. 105.
2. J. VERGHSE and L. M. YEDDANAPALLI, *Chemical Age of India*, 1952, 103.

3. J. OWEN and J. L. SIMONSEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 3001.
4. M. G. RAU, *Indian Forest Records*, 1925, 11, 197.
5. Z. HUSSIAN and B. BHUSHAN, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12A, 287.
6. S. FRYDERK, *U. S. Pat.*, 1945 (Nov. 20), 2389389.
7. A. G. FARBENFABRIKEN BAYER, *Brit. Pat.*, 1954 (July), 712708.
8. H. PINES and W. O. HAAG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 2847.
9. P. SELWOOD and R. P. EISCHENS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1590.
10. J. TURKEVICH *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 1129.
11. V. KRISHNASAMY and L. M. YEDDANAPALLI, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 3046.
12. O. JOHNSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 827
13. A. E. HIRSCHLER and A. SCHNEIDER, *J. Chem. Eng Data*, 1961, 6, 313.
14. I. D. CHAPMAN and M. L. HAIR, *J. Catal.*, 1963, 2, 145.
15. A. N. WEBB, *Ind Eng. Chem.*, 1957, 49, 261.
16. A. E. HIRSCHLER, *J. Catal.*, 1963, 2, 428
17. V. KRISHNASAMY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1960, 33, 1813.
18. I. L. FINAR, "Organic Chemistry", ELBS, 1964, Vol. I, p. 486.
19. E. P. PARRY, *J. Catal.*, 1963, 2, 371.
20. J. W. KNOWLTON and F. D. ROSSINI, *J. Research Nat. Bur. Standards*, 1937, 19, 249 ; 1949, 43, 113.
21. J. R. LACHER, A. KIANPOUR and J. D. PARK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, 61, 1124.
22. H. PINES and C. T. CHEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3562.
23. C. KEMBALL and J. J. ROONY, *Proc. Roy. Soc. (London)*, 1960, 257A, 132.
24. L. E. ORGEL, "An Introduction to Transition Metal Chemistry : Ligand-Field Theory", Methuen and Co Ltd, London, 1960, Chap. 10.
25. J. M. BRIDGES, G. T. RYMER and D. S. McIVER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 871
26. S. E. VOLTZ and S. W. WELLER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, 59, 569.
27. P. W. SELWOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 2676.